

**INTEGRATSION YONDASHUV ASOSIDA BO‘LAJAK O‘QITUVCHILARNI
KASBIY FAOLIYATIGA TAYYORLASHNING PEDAGOGIK
XUSUSIYATLARI**

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Annotatsiya. Maqola integrativ yondashuv bo‘lajak o‘qituvchilarni kasbiy faoliyatga tayyorlashda qanday imkoniyatlar berishi haqida ma‘lumot beradi. Zamonaviy ta‘limda fanlarni integratsiyalashuvi yangi pedagogik yechimlarni faol izlash, ta‘lim oluvchilarga samarali va asosli ta‘sir ko‘rsatish uchun pedagogik xodimlarning ijodiy salohiyatini rivojlantirish yo‘nalishlaridan biridir.

Kalit so‘zlar: fan, integrativ funksiya, transdisiplinar, izchillik, daraja, siyosat, ta‘lim muammolari, ishlab chiqarish, yaxlit tizim.

**ПЕДАГОГИЧЕСКАЯ ОСОБЕННОСТЬ ПРОФЕССИОНАЛЬНОЙ
ПОДГОТОВКИ БУДУЩИХ УЧИТЕЛЕЙ НА ОСНОВЕ
КОМПЛЕКСНОГО ПОДХОДА.**

Аннотация. В статье представлена информация о том, какие возможности предоставляет интегративный подход в подготовке будущих учителей к профессиональной деятельности. Интеграция предметов в современном образовании является одним из способов активного поиска новых педагогических решений, развития творческого потенциала педагогических кадров с целью оказания эффективного и разумного воздействия на учащихся.

Ключевые слова: наука, интегративная функция, трансдисциплинарность, системность, уровень, политика, образовательные проблемы, производство, интегрированная система.

**PEDAGOGICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF PREPARING FUTURE
TEACHERS FOR PROFESSIONAL ACTIVITY ON THE BASIS OF AN
INTEGRATED APPROACH**

Annotation. The article provides information on what opportunities the integrative approach provides in the preparation of future teachers for professional activities. The integration of subjects in modern education is one of the ways to actively search for new pedagogical solutions, to develop the creative potential of pedagogical staff in order to have an effective and reasonable impact on learners.

Key words: science, integrative function, transdisciplinary, consistency, level, policy, educational problems, production, integrated system.

Nowadays, the training of competitive personnel that meets the requirements of the time has become an important issue. A number of changes are being implemented in the country to develop the education sector. Including our presidents, they pay a lot of attention to the field of higher education. Along with the development of the higher education organization, it is also very important to increase the capacity of the educators working in the organization. Our president emphasized in his speech. In the world, in order to ensure the quality of personnel training and employment, special attention is paid to the organization of educational content based on integrated knowledge, the use of a dual system of personnel training based on the integrative approach, the mutual coordination of the cooperative activities of customers and organizational institutions.

1 Let's consider what integration is as a phenomenon from a term and methodological point of view. "Integration" comes from the Latin words *integratio*-restore, fill, integer-whole. Integration is the process and result of achieving the integrity of the educational content by establishing inter-disciplinary and inter-disciplinary relations, interactions between different educational programs.

- system, a concept that indicates the state of dependence of separate differentiated parts and tasks of the organism and the process leading to this state.

- the process of rapprochement of sciences, which is carried out along with the processes of classification. The content of a specific academic subject chosen on the basis of interdisciplinarity consists of some general expressions related to this or that subject. For our time, the integration of sciences is common to have a more coherent vision of the general state of the universe. It is impossible to solve this problem within one discipline. Therefore, in the educational system, the process of combining and expressing the general content of academic subjects in integrated models continues.

Professional training of future teachers based on an integrative approach poses several problems to the educational system. To solve these tasks, in order to scientifically substantiate the interdisciplinary connection of studies, to select the content of each study subject in the interdisciplinary connection, using the latest pedagogical technologies used in the educational process, to interact with one of the study subjects. system should be formed. Interrelated learning of academic subjects allows students to understand the world as a whole. An educator with such competence can organize the activities of centers in preschool educational organizations in an integrative state and enrich the thinking of future teachers with knowledge about the interconnectedness of systems.

There are both advantages and disadvantages of the integrative approach during the professional training of future teachers. Simultaneous education and upbringing in Eastern countries is considered integration. In general, if we consider the world as a whole, any processes taking place in it are inextricably linked. And integration reflects on these relationships. Integration is a process that teaches systematization and simplification of complexity in education.

Integration in education is the process of establishing connections between the components of the content within a certain educational system in order to form a holistic view of the world aimed at the development of the learner's personality and self-development. Integration is a process that teaches systematization and simplification of complexity in education. The integration of subjects in modern education is one of the ways to actively search for new pedagogical solutions, to develop the creative potential of pedagogical staff in order to have an effective and reasonable impact on learners. An integrative approach is an approach that helps prepare students to become specialists in their profession. Integration prevents students from getting scattered knowledge, disintegration of their knowledge, ensures that they acquire integrated knowledge and a set of universal values. . The principle of integration includes all components of the educational process, interconnection of all elements of the system, communication between systems, it is the leader in setting the goal, determining the content of education, its forms and methods. Integrative approach to any pedagogical process.

Integration allows teachers and students to be involved in an active co-creative process. This is a well-thought-out educational and educational process that helps to revise the general structure of educational organization and prepare students for the process of perception. By teaching to understand and analyze information, students form concepts and ideas about the interaction of all processes in the world as a whole. In addition, there are disadvantages and negative consequences of the integrative approach. Y. M. Kolegin and O. L. Aleksinko show the negative factors of integration as follows: "Limited number of educational subjects - the content of a large amount of knowledge acquired can be supplemented by reflecting the real view of the world, the interdependence of its parts;" the need to develop very important reading, writing and numeracy skills.

According to Yu.M. Kolyagin, the concept of "integration" in relation to the education system can have two meanings. Integration can be seen as an educational goal - "creating a student's holistic view of the world around us", educational tools - "finding a common platform for converging subject knowledge". As an educational goal, it provides knowledge that teaches young students to imagine a whole world in which these elements are interconnected. And integration as a learning tool is aimed at developing knowledge, expanding and updating knowledge. At the same time,

integration should only integrate the acquired knowledge into a single system and should not replace the teaching of traditional academic subjects.

A. Ya. We believe that the theory of educational integration developed by Danilyuk. In it, the author reveals the concept of educational integration: "Educational integration is the consistent translation of messages from one educational language to another by the student under the guidance of the teacher, in the process of which knowledge is acquired. , concepts are organized, personal and cultural meanings are born. In other words, it is not a formal combination of different knowledge into a new educational text, but a combination of different texts in the mind of the student, a mental conceptual and leads to the formation of semantic structures.

An important component of the psychological-pedagogical support for the development of innovative pedagogical activity of future teachers based on an integrative approach is their preparation in a higher education institution based on an integrative approach. Even when the attitude of the state to the reconstruction of schools is highly positive, it is necessary to fundamentally change the views of those responsible for training pedagogical personnel. It is necessary to define a long-term strategy of changes, in this strategy, teacher training should be carried out on a different basis, on the basis of direct innovation.

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